

ULTRASONIC WAVE CHARACTERIZATION OF POLYMERS

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ABSTRACT

It is observed experimentally that the phase velocity of a thermoplastic, polycarbonate, is not dependent on frequency over the range 0.5 to 5.0 MHz but is dependent on moderate changes in temperature in the range 25 to 75 °C. The attenuation is found to be highly influenced by temperature changes in the range 25 to 75 °C. The attenuation is shown to increase as the frequency increases. Furthermore, it is observed that the attenuation at frequencies between 4.5 and 5.0 MHz is a maximum at a phase velocity of approximately 2230 m/sec. The gain percent of amplitude defined as $G\% = (O/I) \cdot 100$ (where O =output voltage, I =input voltage) is found to be independent of the magnitude of input voltage (which is less than 80 volt) to the transmitter transducer. The relaxation function of the test material is evaluated by employing a theoretical development in which the experimentally determined attenuation and phase velocity are utilized.

INTRODUCTION

Viscoelastic properties can be of enormous importance in materials characterization and nondestructive evaluation. The matrix components of many composites are polymeric materials which normally exhibit either linear or nonlinear viscoelastic responses under moderate loads or temperatures.

Ultrasonic nondestructive evaluation techniques have been utilized to characterize polymeric materials, among others, although it has been claimed that ultrasonics are not practical for the characterization of polymeric materials because of their high attenuation of stress wave signals. The high attenuation in polymeric materials is, however, considered an advantage for echo pattern interpretation in which pure wave modes may be obtained due to the insensitivity of the ultrasonic wave to sidewall reflections[1].

An ultrasonic technique was used to characterize the curing of epoxies[2]. Ultrasonic wave speed and attenuation were used to monitor cure and a simple model consisting of linear springs and a dashpot was proposed to quantify appropriate material constants such as storage and loss stiffnesses. This technique has also been used to characterize solid polymeric materials such as polycarbonate, polysulfone and polyether sulfone[3].

For the characterization of stress relaxation in polymeric materials, only a few studies utilizing ultrasonic speed and attenuation have been published as contrasted to the numerous investigations employing mechanical impact tests. A theoretical study of the propagation of ultrasonic waves in nonlinear viscoelastic solids was used to distinguish stress relaxation behavior of polymethylmethacrylate[4].

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This paper presents an experimental investigation of ultrasonic wave propagation in polycarbonate specimens having varying thickness. Ultrasonic attenuation and phase velocity are measured at various temperatures over the range 25 to 75 °C. The wave frequencies ranged from 0.5 to 5.0 MHz. The experimentally obtained phase velocities and attenuations versus frequency are utilized to estimate the relaxation functions of a polycarbonate.

EXPERIMENTS

Material and Specimen

The specimen material was Lexan polycarbonate sheet. The physical properties were as follows: specific gravity, 1.21; coefficient of linear thermal expansion, 37.5×10^{-5} cm/cm °C; glass transition temperature, 145 °C. The specimen material was initially stress free. The specimen configuration used in this study, which was originally designed for creep tests, is shown in Fig. 1.

Procedure and Equipment

A chamber enclosing the specimens, transducers and two photographic lights (which were used to control temperature in the chamber) was constructed. The ultrasonic measurements were made by the through transmission technique using specimens having varying thicknesses. General features of the chamber system are shown in Fig. 2.

The transmitting transducer was excited with a tone burst voltage at various voltages (peak to peak); this signal introduced a stress wave into the specimen. After travelling through the specimen, the signal was captured by the receiving transducer and displayed on an oscilloscope. The velocity measurements of the ultrasonic waves in the through transmission configuration may be affected by many parameters, including the transducer-specimen interface pressure, the mechanical and chemical properties and thickness of the couplant, the alignment between the specimen and the transducer, the nonparallelism of the faces of the specimen and the inherent time delay of the electrical system. To minimize these effects, the steps recommended in Refs. [5 and 6] were followed.

In evaluating the velocity, the time shift between the same individual cycle of the input and output signals was measured. Typical examples of the input and output signals are shown in Fig. 3. A few leading cycles were not used because of their transient nature. In order to cancel the inherent time delay due to the electrical system, otherwise identical specimens of varying thickness were used. If the time shifts for specimens of thicknesses L_1 are t_1 , respectively, the phase velocity v can be expressed as

$$v = \frac{(L_2 - L_1)}{(t_2 - t_1)} \quad (1)$$

The tests were conducted at various input frequencies ranging from 0.5 to 5.0 MHz under three different temperature conditions, namely, 25 °C, 45 °C and 75 °C. The temperature variation during each test was less than 1 °C. The selected frequencies depended on the frequency range of operation of the transducers. The transducer-specimen interface pressure was maintained at 0.43 MPa during all the tests. This value was slightly above the saturation pressure [6] and guaranteed a stable output.

Attenuation measurements were made by comparing the relative amplitudes of the received signal through two different thicknesses of polycarbonate having the same cross section. The necessary equations can be generated by the following arguments. The amplitude of the stress wave at any location x along the thickness of the specimen can be expressed as $F_i(\omega, T)A_{ii} \exp(-\alpha x)$, where α is the attenuation of the test material and is both temperature and frequency dependent. A_{ii} is the input voltage amplitude corresponding to a specimen of thickness L_i . $F_i(\omega, T)$ is a function of frequency, ω , and temperature, T , and is formally the transduction ratio for the

electromechanical gyrating system corresponding to the transformation of an input electrical voltage to a mechanical stress wave in the specimen [7]. The output, A_{o1} , of the receiving transducer after passing through the interface between the specimen and receiving transducer is

$$A_{o1} = A_{i1} e^{-\alpha L_1} F_1(\omega, T) F_2(\omega, T) \quad (2)$$

where $F_2(\omega, T)$ = transduction constant corresponding to an output electrical voltage and includes both the characteristics of receiver and the stress wave transmissibility of the transducer-specimen interface.

For the specimen with thickness L_2 the same argument may be followed to obtain the output amplitude, A_{o2} , as

$$A_{o2} = A_{i2} e^{-\alpha L_2} F_1(\omega, T) F_2(\omega, T) \quad (3)$$

where A_{i2} = input amplitude of a specimen with thickness L_2 .

It was assumed that the transduction constants, $F_1(\omega, T)$ and $F_2(\omega, T)$, were dependent on the frequency and temperature, but not on the input amplitude. The attenuation coefficient, α , thus can be expressed as

$$\alpha = \frac{\text{Log}_e \frac{A_{o1}}{A_{o2}} - \text{Log}_e \frac{A_{i1}}{A_{i2}}}{L_2 - L_1} \quad (4)$$

The attenuation coefficient, α , can be determined by measuring the input and output amplitudes for which the input amplitudes need not be constant.

RESULTS and DISCUSSIONS

In this experimental investigation the main concern was how the ultrasonic output varied according to different chamber conditions, including temperature, magnitude of input signals and input frequencies. Although preparation was made to observe nonlinear effects in the ultrasonic output in terms of phase velocity, attenuation and the wave profile in the time domain, it was found that the experimental results were within the linear region. This section will present the main results obtained.

The gain percents defined as $G\% = (O/I) \cdot 100$ (where O =output voltage, I =input voltage) were found to be independent of the magnitude of the input voltage (which was less than 80 volts). This finding shows that the tests were conducted within the linear region of the specimen material.

Fig. 4 shows a relationship between the phase velocity and frequency. At a given temperature, the measured phase velocity was not dependent on frequency over the range 0.5 to 5.0 MHz. The phase velocity, however, decreased linearly as temperature increased, independent of wave frequency. The confidence level of the velocity measurements was 99 percent.

Attenuation versus frequency for different temperatures is shown in Fig. 5. As shown in Fig. 5, the attenuation was highly influenced by temperature. The attenuation increased as the specimen temperature decreased. However, it was interesting to note that as the frequency increased from 0.5 to 4 MHz, the attenuation curve for the 45 °C test crossed that for the 25 °C test at a frequency of approximately 4 MHz. This phenomenon indicated that the attenuation of the specimen tested at 45 °C increased more rapidly than that of tests conducted at 25 °C. The attenuation curve for the 75 °C closely approached that for 45 °C tests at a frequency of

approximately 5.0 MHz implying that it would cross the curve for the 45 °C tests at a higher frequency than 5.0 MHz. Further investigation is needed for the rigorous physical interpretation of this phenomenon.

Fig. 6 shows attenuation versus phase velocity. It was observed that the attenuation increased as the phase velocity of ultrasonic stress wave increased. However, the attenuation at frequencies between 4.5 and 5.0 MHz was a maximum at approximately 2230 m/sec of phase velocity. The attenuation per wavelength, λ , versus temperature is shown in Fig. 7. These results indicated that there was a temperature where the attenuation was maximum at different frequencies. This phenomenon might be interpreted as the β -relaxation as noted in Ref.[8] in which the rotation of the molecule segment played a role and its mobility seemed to be dependent on the frequency and temperature. The details of this matter should be further investigated.

In estimating the relaxation functions of the test material, a theoretical development in Ref.[9] was utilized. The main results are summarized as shown in the following equation.

$$G(t) = \frac{2}{\pi} \int_0^t \int_0^\infty \left(\frac{\rho_R C_p^2(\omega)}{\sec 2\phi(\omega) \left\{ \left[\alpha(\omega) \frac{C_p(\omega)}{\omega} \right]^2 + 1 \right\}} - \rho_R C_\infty^2 \right) \cos(\omega t) d\omega dt + \rho_R C_\infty^2 \quad (5)$$

where

$$\phi(\omega) = \tan^{-1} \left[\frac{\alpha(\omega) C_p(\omega)}{\omega} \right], \quad \rho_R = \text{mass density at reference state}$$

$$C_\infty = \lim_{\omega \rightarrow \infty} C_p(\omega), \quad \omega = \text{radian frequency}$$

$$\alpha = \text{wave attenuation}, \quad C_p = \text{phase velocity}$$

$$G(t) = \text{stress relaxation function}$$

To evaluate the stress relaxation function from the ultrasonic experimental data, the integrand, $I(\omega)$, in eqn. (5)

$$I(\omega) = \frac{\rho_R C_p^2(\omega)}{\sec 2\phi(\omega) \left\{ \left[\alpha(\omega) \frac{C_p(\omega)}{\omega} \right]^2 + 1 \right\}} - \rho_R C_\infty^2 \quad (6)$$

was evaluated at N points which were equally spaced in the frequency domain. The integrand could thus be represented by the series [9]

$$I(\omega) = \sum_{i=1}^N e^{\left(\frac{-\omega}{W_i} \right)} F_i(\omega) \quad \text{where } W_i = \text{weighted value at the } i^{\text{th}} \text{ data point} \quad (7)$$

Eqn. (7) was rewritten in matrix form as

$$|I| = |Q| |F| \quad \text{where} \quad |Q| = \begin{pmatrix} e^{-\frac{\omega_1}{W_1}} & e^{-\frac{\omega_1}{W_2}} & \dots & e^{-\frac{\omega_1}{W_n}} \\ e^{-\frac{\omega_2}{W_1}} & e^{-\frac{\omega_2}{W_2}} & \dots & e^{-\frac{\omega_2}{W_n}} \\ \dots & \dots & \dots & \dots \\ e^{-\frac{\omega_n}{W_1}} & e^{-\frac{\omega_n}{W_2}} & \dots & e^{-\frac{\omega_n}{W_n}} \end{pmatrix} \quad (7a)$$

$$|I| = |I(\omega_1) \quad I(\omega_2) \dots I(\omega_n)|^T \quad (7b)$$

$$|F| = |F_1(\omega_1) \quad F_2(\omega_2) \dots F_n(\omega_n)|^T \quad (7c)$$

and $|F|$ was determined by $|F| = |Q|^{-1} |I|$. Then, $G(t)$ was expressed as

$$G(t) = \frac{2}{\pi} \sum_{i=1}^N F_i(\omega) \tan^{-1}(W_i t) + \rho_R C_\infty^2 \quad \text{where} \quad t = \text{time} \quad (8)$$

It was assumed that the change in mass density during the tests was 0% and 1.0% at 45 °C and 75 °C, respectively. And the phase velocity at infinite frequency, C_∞ , under a particular temperature was considered to be identical with those estimated at frequencies over the range 0.5 to 5.0 MHz in this study. The numerically determined $F_i(\omega)$ and $G(t)$, are shown in Fig. 8 and Fig. 9, respectively. It was interesting to note that the relaxation function followed a sigmoidal path as time increased logarithmically. It was found that the order of magnitude of the relaxation function approached the static elastic moduli of 3.14 Gpa, 2.53 Gpa and 1.72 Gpa for 25 °C, 45 °C and 75 °C, respectively, of the test material as the time increased.

CONCLUDING REMARKS

It was shown that the gain percent of amplitude, defined as $G\% = (O/I) \cdot 100$ (where; O = output voltage, I = input voltage), is independent of the magnitude of the input voltage to the transmitter transducer. Moreover, it was found that a thermoplastic, polycarbonate, is nondispersive over the frequency range 0.5 to 5.0 MHz. But the phase velocity showed a strong dependence on moderate changes of temperature over the range 25 to 75 °C.

The attenuation was found to be highly influenced by temperature within the range of this investigation. It was shown that the attenuation increased as the frequency increased and the slope of individual curves relating attenuation and frequency was shown to be influenced by the specimen temperature and frequency. Furthermore, it was observed that the attenuation at a frequency between 4.5 and 5.0 MHz was a maximum at a phase velocity of approximately 2230 m/sec. There needs to be further investigation to interpret many of these physical phenomena more rigorously.

By utilizing the experimentally determined phase velocity and attenuation for different temperatures versus various frequency, the relaxation functions at different temperatures were estimated. It was found that the magnitudes of the relaxation functions approach the static elastic moduli of the test material as time increased.

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REFERENCES

- [1] B.Bridge, An Appraisal of Ultrasonic Methods for the Nondestructive Evaluation of Particle and Fibre-Filled Thermoplastics, British Journal of NDT, September 1987, pp. 326-331.
- [2] H.T.Hahn, "Application of Ultrasonic Technique to Cure Characterization of Epoxies, Nondestructive Methods for Material Property Determination, ed. by C.O.Rudd and R.E.Green, Plenum, New York, 1983, pp. 315-326.
- [3] D.W.Phillips, A.M.North and R.A.Pethrick, "Ultrasonic Studies of Polycarbonate., Polysulfone and Polyether Sulfone", J. of Applied Polymer Science, Vol.21, 1977, pp. 1859-1867.
- [4] J.W.Nunziato and H.J.Sutherland, "Acoustical Determination of Stress Relaxation Functions for Polymers", J. of Applied Physics, Vol.44, No1, 1973, pp. 184-187.
- [5] E.R.C.Marques and J.H.Williams, Jr., "Ultrasonic Determination of the Elastic Constants of the Stiffness Matrix for Unidirectional Fiberglass Epoxy Composites", NASA Contractor Report 4043, December 1986.
- [6] J.H.Williams, Jr., H.N.Hashemi and S.S.Lee, "Ultrasonic Attenuation and Velocity in AS/3501-6 Graphite/Epoxy Composite", J. of Nondestructive Evaluation, Vol.1, No.2, 1980, pp. 137-148.
- [7] S.S.Lee and J.H.Williams, Jr., "Stress-Wave Attenuation in Thin Structures by Ultrasonic Through-Transmission", J. of Nondestructive Evaluation, Vol.1, No.4, 1980, pp. 277-286
- [8] I.L.Hopkins and C.R.Kurkjian, "Relaxation Spectra and Relaxation Process in Solid Polymers and Glasses", Physical Acoustics, Vol. II-Part B, 1965, pp. 91-163.
- [9] J.W.Nunziato, E.K.Walsh, K.W.Schuler and L.M.Barker, "Wave Propagation in Nonlinear Viscoelastic Solids", Handbuch der Physik, Band VIa/4, ed. by C.Truesdell, 1974, pp. 1-99.

FIG. 1 SPECIMEN GEOMETRY.

FIG. 2 SCHEMATIC OF EXPERIMENTAL SYSTEM.

FIG. 3 TYPICAL INPUT AND OUTPUT SIGNALS.

FIG. 4 PHASE VELOCITY VERSUS FREQUENCY.

FIG. 5 ATTENUATION VERSUS FREQUENCY

FIG. 6 ATTENUATION VERSUS PHASE VELOCITY.

FIG. 7 (ATTENUATION/λ) VERSUS TEMPERATURE.
(λ = WAVELENGTH (mm))

FIG. 8 $F(\omega)$ VERSUS FREQUENCY.

FIG. 9 RELAXATION FUNCTIONS VERSUS TIME.